

Section on Obstetrics

Dr. Geo. C. Mosher, Chairman, Kansas City, Mo.
 Dr. Calvin R. Hannah, Vice-Chairman, Dallas, Tex.
 Dr. Jas. R. Garber, Secretary, Birmingham, Ala.

Section on Eye, Ear, Nose and Throat

Dr. W. T. Patton, Chairman, New Orleans, La.
 Dr. H. H. Briggs, Vice-Chairman, Asheville, N. C.
 Dr. John J. Shea, Secretary, Memphis, Tenn.

Section on Public Health

Dr. S. W. Welch, Chairman, Montgomery, Ala.
 Dr. P. W. Covington, Vice-Chmn, Louisville, Ky.
 Dr. Henry Boswell, Secretary, Sanatoriu, Miss.

National Malaria Committee (Conference on Malaria)

Meets Conjointly with Southern Medical Association

Dr. H. S. Cumming, Surgeon General, U. S. Public Health Service, Honorary Chairman, Washington, D. C.

Dr. W. S. Leathers, Chairman, Jackson, Miss.
 Dr. L. D. Fricks, Surgeon, U. S. Public Health Service, Secretary, Memphis, Tenn.

Conference on Medical Education

Dr. Douglas VanderHoof, Chmn, Richmond, Va.
 Dr. Kenneth M. Lynch, Vice-Chairman, Charleston, S. C.

Dr. I. I. Lemann, Secretary, New Orleans, La.

*Southern Hospital Association
 Auxiliary of Southern Medical Association*

Dr. W. P. Harbin, President, Rome, Ga.
 Dr. Beverley R. Tucker, Vice-Pres., Richmond, Va.
 Dr. Paul V. Anderson, Secretary, Richmond, Va.

Women Physicians of the Southern Medical Association

Dr. Elizabeth Kane, President, Memphis, Tenn.
 Dr. Florence Brandeis, First Vice-President, Louisville, Ky.
 Dr. Iva Youmans, Second Vice-Pres., Miami, Fla.
 Dr. Josephine Hunt, Sec'y-Treas., Lexington, Ky.

Book Reviews

The Catarrhal and Suppurative Diseases of the Accessory Sinuses of the Nose. By Ross Hall Skillern, M.D., Professor of Laryngology, Medico-Chirurgical College, Post-Graduate School, University of Pennsylvania; Late Lieutenant-Colonel, M. C. U. S. A.; Fellow of American Laryngological Society; Fellow of the American College of Surgeons; Fellow of the American Laryngological, Rhinological and Otolological Society; Fellow of the New York Academy of Medicine, etc. 300 illustrations. Third edition, thoroughly revised and enlarged. Philadelphia and London: J. B. Lippincott Co.

The author in the third edition of his well known and deservedly popular treatise has thoroughly revised and brought up to date the subject matter of former editions, and in addition has incorporated a careful study of the influence exerted by sinus disease on the general system, especially the amount or degree of incapacity produced in the individual. Also the results of his observations and experience with injuries and wounds of the sinuses while with the American Expeditionary Forces in France have been incorporated. The book is well written and handsomely illustrated and ranks with the best of the year.

The After-Treatment of Surgical Patients. By Willard Bartlett, A.M., M.D., F.A.C.S., and Collaborators. Vol. I with 222 original illustrations and 1 color plate; Vol. II with 213 original illustrations; 1,093 pages. St. Louis: C. V. Mosby Co., 1920.

A large part of Vol. I is written by Dr. McKittrick, Dr. Bartlett's house surgeon, and is sufficiently clear to be read by nurses. The first part, particularly, should be invaluable to the discussion of post-operative nausea is good, of ileus, fat embolism, heat stroke, thrombosis, and the common and rare post-operative complications. There is a discussion of all the views as to the cause of incongruity and non-coagulability of the blood. The theory of Fauchaux, that this is caused by increased sodium content due to kidney insufficiency, or sepsis, heart derangement, or infection, is described. He concludes with Wesson that the important factors in post-operative thrombosis are: Injury of vessel walls; slowing of the blood stream; destruction of corpuscles from a toxic substance; bacteremia.

The essays on pyelephlebitis are good. The largest part of Vol. II is by Bartlett himself. It covers a large field. In taking up the after-treatment, he discusses operations on the neck, thorax, abdomen, liver, spleen, gall bladder, female pelvic organs, and amputations. It is an excellent resume and is of great practical value.

Pulmonary Tuberculosis. By Maurice Fishberg, M.D., Clinical Professor of Medicine, New York University and Bellevue Hospital Medical College; Attending Physician, Montefiore Home and Hospital for Chronic Diseases, New York. Second edition, revised and enlarged. Illustrated with 160 engravings and 25 plates. 744 pages. New York: Lea & Febiger.

Information for the general practitioner, to aid in the early recognition and treatment of tuberculous or pre-tuberculous conditions, is easily available here. The tubercle bacilli, their morphology, methods of determining their presence, phthisis and phthisiogenesis, are discussed at length. There is a very full description of symptoms in the gastro-intestinal tract, of symptoms referable to the cardiovascular and renal systems, of various methods of treatment of pulmonary tuberculosis, such as the rest cure, open air, climatic treatment, institutional treatment, medicinal, dietetic, and operative.

The entire subject is deeply and methodically handled. The book is a compendium of modern knowledge of this very prevalent disease.

Symptoms in the Diagnosis of Disease. By Hobart Amory Hare, M.D., B.Sc., Professor Therapeutics and Diagnosis, Jefferson Medical College. Eighth edition, thoroughly revised. 562 pages. Illustrated with 195 engravings and 9 plates. Philadelphia: Lea & Febiger, 1920.

That modern laboratory methods have diverted the former careful study of the patient is apparent everywhere. Just as important now as ever before is the diagnosis based upon carefully elicited and correlated symptoms, with the laboratory to aid, or to check the opinion based on symptoms. This is the ideal way to practice medicine. The above facts underlie the whole text as written by Dr. Hare, and that this book is in its eighth edition is proof of its merit and the welcome reception by the profession.

A Manual of Physical Diagnosis. By Austin Flint, M.D. Eighth edition, revised by Henry C. Thacher, M.S., M.D., Asst. Prof. Clin. Medicine, College of P. & S., Columbia University. 362 pages. Illustrated. Philadelphia: Lea & Febiger, 1920.

There is an ever increasing demand for careful physical examination in the practice of medicine, and rightly so. This manual has always been considered a medical classic. Nearly every doctor has used or referred to it during his medical course. This last edition contains valuable chapters on the disorders and the arrhythmias of the heart, based on recent studies of the effort syndrome or the soldier's heart. Many other valuable additions are to be observed. Certainly, it is worth the time of every physician to read and study this little manual again.

BOOK REVIEWS

(Continued on page 89)